

OGLAP

Offline Grid Location Addressing Protocol

Technical White Paper and Protocol Specification

*A Deterministic, Offline-First, Human-friendly, and Administratively Anchored
Digital Addressing System for Emerging Economies*

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Repositories:

<https://github.com/Guinee-IO/oglap-ggp-node-js>

<https://github.com/Guinee-IO/oglap-ggp-python-sdk>

<https://github.com/Guinee-IO/oglap-ggp-dart-fl>

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1. Executive Summary

An estimated four billion people worldwide live without a formal street address. This deficit is overwhelmingly concentrated in Sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, Latin America, and the informal urban settlements of the developing world. Far from a mere logistical inconvenience, the absence of standardized addressing infrastructure constitutes a fundamental structural barrier to human and economic development: it impedes the delivery of essential public services, obstructs economic participation, undermines emergency response capability, constrains the growth of the digital economy, and forecloses access to financial instruments that depend on precise and verifiable domicile information. It is a barrier that persists, paradoxically, even as global connectivity and technological capability accelerate.

Two digital addressing systems have emerged as the principal attempts to remedy this gap: What3Words (W3W), a proprietary system that encodes locations as three-word combinations; and Google Plus Codes (Open Location Code), an open-source alphanumeric geocoding scheme. While each has achieved measurable adoption, neither has proven adequate for the specific requirements of developing nations, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, characterized by low literacy rates, unreliable connectivity and fragmented administrative hierarchies.

This white paper introduces the **Offline Grid Location Addressing Protocol (OGLAP)**, a deterministic, offline-first digital addressing system that proposes a new approach through a fundamentally different architectural premise: the anchoring of geocodes within the existing administrative and territorial structure of the country in which they operate. Unlike W3W and Plus Codes, which rely on abstract global grids disconnected from local governance, OGLAP generates codes that are hierarchically embedded within recognised administrative divisions, from national boundaries down to neighborhoods, quartiers, and villages.

At the heart of the protocol is a dual-format addressing model that decouples machine-level precision from human usability without compromising either. At its core, the system generates a complete hierarchical code, such as: **GN-CON-QYTC-B0B1-2282** which encodes country, region, locality, and micro-location at sub-meter precision. This format is optimized for machine-to-machine communication, database integration, and system interoperability.

In parallel, OGLAP derives a human-friendly address representation from this same code: **B0B1-2282 Yattaya Fossede, Conakry, Guinea**. This “human address” retains the precise micro-location identifier while integrating clear, familiar local references, producing a format that is natural to read, speak, remember, write on document, and interpret.

This dual-format design is central to OGLAP's innovation. Rather than forcing a trade-off between technical accuracy and human usability, the protocol ensures both simultaneously:

Machines interact with full structured codes, People interact with intuitive, locally meaningful addresses.

This approach enhances spatial intuition, improves memorability, supports low-literacy environments, and aligns digital addressing with existing social and administrative realities.

OGLAP is designed to be country-agnostic in specification yet country-specific in deployment. The protocol requires three centralized configuration files that define the territorial profile, locality naming conventions, and geospatial reference data for any target country. The result is a system that can operate entirely offline, with zero dependency on external APIs or network connectivity, while remaining fully interoperable across systems.

Licensed under MIT with attribution, OGLAP represents a transparent, territorially anchored, and human-centric approach to digital addressing - one that prioritizes institutional adoption, cognitive accessibility, and long-term infrastructural resilience.

2. The Global Addressing Crisis: Problem Statement

2.1. Scale and Severity of the Addressing Deficit

The International Telecommunication Union and the Universal Postal Union estimate that approximately 4 billion individuals globally reside in locations that lack formal [1], machine-readable addresses. This deficit is often associated with informal settlements, yet it extends well beyond them. Even in formally planned urban areas across many developing countries, addressing systems remain incomplete, inconsistent, or entirely absent. Globally, as much as half of urban environments are still poorly addressed, and in Africa alone an estimated 440 million people, nearly 30 percent of the population, lack a formal address [2].

In Sub-Saharan Africa, the challenge is particularly acute because of the scale of informality: more than half of the urban population lives in informal settlements, where structured addressing systems have rarely been implemented. In some countries, explaining your location to a delivery service can take longer than time required to drive to the location. Looking ahead, the United Nations Human Settlements Programme (UN-Habitat) projects that the region will have approximately 922.6 million informal settlement residents by 2050, accounting for 31.8 percent of the global total of 2.9 billion [2].

2.2. The Institutional Dimension

The addressing crisis is not merely a technical problem amenable to technological resolution alone. It is deeply entwined with governance, land tenure, and administrative capacity. In many developing nations, the territorial hierarchy, from national boundaries through regions (in the guinean context, prefectures, sub-prefectures, communes, and quartiers), constitutes the primary framework through which the state exercises authority and delivers services. Any addressing system that operates independently of this hierarchy may face inherent resistance from the institutions that would be required to adopt and enforce it.

This institutional dimension explains, in substantial part, the limited penetration of existing digital addressing systems in the very markets they claim to serve. A system that assigns abstract codes to geographic coordinates, without referencing the administrative units that govern those locations, fails to integrate with the bureaucratic, legal, and civic processes that an addressing system is ultimately intended to support.

2.3. Requirements for an Effective Solution

- **Cognitive accessibility**

Addresses must be usable by populations with limited formal literacy, whose competencies often center on basic alphabetic recognition and numeracy. This necessitates formats that minimise cognitive load: short segments, familiar character sets, and structural regularity. Systems that rely on long alphanumeric strings or linguistically complex constructs risk

exclusion through error, ambiguity, and poor recall. Accessibility must therefore be treated as a primary design constraint, not an afterthought.

- **Administrative alignment**

The addressing system must be anchored in the existing territorial and administrative hierarchy of the state. In many developing countries, governance, public service delivery, and civic identity are organized around nested administrative units, like regions, prefectures, communes, and quartiers or villages. A system that ignores this structure introduces friction at the institutional level, as it cannot be readily integrated into bureaucratic processes, legal frameworks, or public service delivery mechanisms. Conversely, alignment with these structures embeds the system within the operational logic of the state, enabling immediate applicability for governance, planning, and administration.

- **Deterministic reproducibility**

The system must be strictly deterministic, producing identical outputs from identical inputs regardless of device, time, or execution context. This property ensures consistency across users, platforms, and jurisdictions, eliminating discrepancies that could undermine trust or introduce ambiguity in critical use cases such as emergency response, land registration, or legal documentation. Determinism is also foundational to interoperability: a code generated in one environment must be universally resolvable.

- **Offline functionality**

The system must operate entirely without reliance on network connectivity. In many target environments, connectivity is intermittent, degraded, or economically inaccessible. An effective addressing solution must therefore execute all core functions locally, including encoding, decoding, and validation, without dependence on APIs or remote infrastructure.

- **Openness and transparency**

The system must be fully open to inspection, audit, and modification. In the context of national infrastructure, proprietary or opaque systems introduce unacceptable risks for public institutions, including vendor lock-in, lack of accountability, and dependency on external entities. An open and transparent system enables governments and institutions to independently validate its operation, adapt it to local requirements, and maintain sovereign control over its evolution.

- **High spatial precision**

The system must provide sufficient resolution to uniquely identify individual dwellings, structures, or points of interest. Addressing at the level of neighborhoods or city blocks is insufficient for many practical applications, including last-mile service delivery, emergency response, logistics, and cadastral mapping. Precision must therefore extend to the granularity required for actionable location reference, while remaining efficient in representation and usable in low-resource environments.

3. Survey of Existing Digital Addressing Systems

3.1. What3Words (W3W)

3.1.1. Technical Overview

What3Words divides the entirety of Earth's surface into a fixed global grid comprising approximately ~57 trillion cells, each measuring three metres by three metres [3]. Each cell is assigned a unique address consisting of three dictionary words, drawn from a curated vocabulary of approximately 25,000 to 40,000 words per supported language. The mapping from geographic coordinates to word triplets is effected through a deterministic algorithm employing linear congruence for pseudo-randomisation, ensuring that geographically proximate cells receive maximally dissimilar word combinations to reduce the risk of confusion.

The system was developed in London, United Kingdom, and launched commercially in 2013. It has since been adopted by a number of governmental, postal, and emergency service organisations, including Mongolia's national postal service, the postal systems of Côte d'Ivoire and Djibouti, and over 85 percent of British emergency service teams as of September 2021 [3], [5].

3.1.2. Assessment and Adoption Gaps

What3Words has achieved meaningful adoption in certain contexts, yet exhibits characteristics that may limit its effectiveness in developing-nation deployments:

Proprietary Enclosure: The W3W algorithm is copyrighted, patented in multiple jurisdictions, and distributed only through encrypted, closed-source implementations. The word lists are proprietary intellectual property. For governments and critical infrastructure operators, this proprietary posture creates dependency on a single commercial entity and limits the capacity for independent audit or modification.

Cognitive Accessibility Constraints: The three-word format relies on vocabulary that may be unfamiliar, difficult to recall, or linguistically unintuitive for populations with limited formal literacy. Variations in pronunciation, spelling errors, and unfamiliar word usage can introduce ambiguity and reduce usability, particularly in oral communication. This dependency on memorization of arbitrary word combinations may hinder adoption in precisely the contexts where accessibility is most critical.

Absence of Administrative Integration: W3W codes bear no relationship to administrative territorial divisions. A W3W address provides no indication of the country, region, prefecture, or locality in which the coded location resides. This abstraction renders the system less intuitive for administrative processes that are inherently territorial.

Lack of Spatial Intuition and Standalone Interpretability:

W3W codes do not convey any inherent information about proximity, direction, or relative position. Adjacent locations may be encoded as entirely dissimilar word triplets (e.g., “*///dunes.taxed.marginal*” and “*///depravity.print.cookie*”), with no visible relationship between them. As a result, in the absence of the application, users have no practical means

of inferring whether a location is nearby or distant, or even within the same region or country. This lack of structural or spatial cues makes independent orientation impossible and reinforces reliance on the application layer, limiting the system's effectiveness in offline or low-resource contexts.

3.2. Google Plus Codes (Open Location Code)

3.2.1. Technical Overview

Google Plus Codes, formally designated as Open Location Code (OLC), employ a recursive grid subdivision algorithm that partitions Earth's surface into progressively smaller cells. The encoding utilises a twenty-character alphanumeric set (deliberately excluding vowels and visually confusable characters) to produce codes of up to fifteen digits, with a plus sign delimiter inserted after the eighth digit for visual parsing. A standard ten-digit Plus Code resolves to a cell of approximately fourteen metres by fourteen metres; maximum precision yields cells of approximately 3.5 metres square.

Released under the Apache 2.0 open-source licence, Plus Codes are integrated into the Google Maps ecosystem and are available on more than ten billion devices globally [7]. The algorithm is fully documented, deterministic, and capable of complete offline operation without lookup tables or external dependencies.

3.2.2. Assessment and Adoption Gaps

Plus Codes represent a technically sound and openly governed system, yet they exhibit characteristics that may constrain their effectiveness in certain developing-nation contexts:

Cognitive Accessibility in Low-Literacy Contexts: The alphanumeric format, combining letters and digits in extended sequences such as 7FG8+5VQ8+3Q, may present challenges for populations with limited formal education. No published usability study has validated the system's effectiveness with low-literacy populations or demonstrated optimal recall and transcription accuracy in these contexts.

Absence of Administrative Context: Like W3W, Plus Codes encode abstract geographic coordinates without reference to administrative or territorial structures. This abstraction limits the system's utility for applications organized along territorial lines, such as postal distribution, administrative aggregation, and governance.

Shortened Code Ambiguity: Plus Codes offer a shortened format that omits the leading characters, requiring a reference location within approximately forty kilometres to disambiguate. This design choice introduces contextual dependency that may limit utility in offline scenarios or where reference data is sparse.

Ecosystem Dependency Considerations: While the algorithm is open source, the practical utility of Plus Codes for end users is substantially dependent on their integration with Google Maps. In contexts where alternative mapping platforms are preferred by government or where data sovereignty concerns militate against reliance on foreign technology platforms, this ecosystem integration may present adoption barriers.

3.3. Structural Limitations of Existing Systems

Both What3Words and Plus Codes represent important technological contributions to the global addressing challenge. However, both are designed as global systems that treat Earth's surface as a uniform coordinate plane, without regard for the administrative, political, or cultural structures that govern the territories they encode. This design philosophy optimises for universality at the expense of institutional alignment.

Neither system produces codes that embed the administrative division in which a location resides, nor does either anchor its grid to the territorial boundaries that define governance, service delivery, and civic identity.

These characteristics reflect a design philosophy that prioritises technical generality and global applicability. For many use cases, this is an appropriate design choice. For addressing systems intended to support institutional integration, administrative aggregation, and cognitive accessibility in developing contexts, however, territorial anchoring and administrative embeddedness become critical requirements.

4. Introducing OGLAP: Design Philosophy and Rationale

The Offline Grid Location Addressing Protocol (OGLAP) was conceived to address the structural requirements identified in the preceding analysis. Its design philosophy rests on five foundational principles that distinguish it from both incumbent systems and from the broader tradition of geocoding-as-abstraction.

Administrative Territorial Anchoring: OGLAP codes are not abstract identifiers imposed upon a featureless coordinate plane. They are hierarchically structured references that embed the administrative context of the encoded location (country, region, locality, and sub-locality) directly within the code itself. A citizen, a postal worker, or a government official who reads an OGLAP code can immediately identify not only the approximate geographic location but also the administrative jurisdiction in which it falls. This anchoring aligns the addressing system with the institutional architecture of the state, reducing the adoption friction.

Offline-First Determinism: OGLAP is architected for environments where network connectivity is unavailable, unreliable, or prohibitively expensive. Once the three required configuration files are loaded into an application's local storage, all encoding and decoding operations execute entirely on-device with zero network dependency. The encoding algorithm is purely deterministic: identical coordinates produce identical LAP codes on any device, at any time, with any basemap, in any language. There is no API to query, no server to authenticate against, and no cloud service that can be throttled, deprecated, or monetised.

Cognitive Accessibility: OGLAP codes are explicitly designed for populations with limited formal literacy but functional familiarity with alphabetic characters and basic numeracy. Rather than treating accessibility as an emergent property, the protocol embeds it directly into the structure of the code. Each segment is short, regular, and uses simple, recognisable character patterns, reducing cognitive load in reading, transcription, and oral communication. Crucially, cognitive accessibility in OGLAP is achieved by design through structural differentiation. Each segment of the code follows a distinct and predictable format, enabling users to recognise and interpret components intuitively without requiring full decoding.

Open-Source Sovereignty: OGLAP is released under the MIT License, with attribution [10]. This licence ensures that OGLAP will remain permanently free and open, and that no entity can appropriate the protocol for proprietary enclosure. Governments, institutions, and communities can deploy, modify, audit, and govern OGLAP without commercial dependency, licensing fees, or intellectual property constraints.

Country-Agnostic Portability: While the reference implementation targets the Republic of Guinea (GGP / OGLAP-GN), the OGLAP protocol is designed for deployment in any country. The protocol specification is decoupled from country-specific data through three externalised JSON configuration files that define the territorial profile, administrative naming conventions, and geospatial reference data. To deploy OGLAP in a new country, one need only prepare these three files in conformity with the documented schema - the encoding engine itself requires no modification.

5. Technical Architecture of the OGLAP Protocol

5.1. Hierarchical Code Structure

An OGLAP Location Addressing Protocol (LAP) code encodes a geographic location at four or five hierarchical levels, each corresponding to a progressively more granular administrative or spatial unit. The protocol defines two grid strategies: local and national. The 2 grid strategies are employed depending on the availability of fine-grained administrative boundary data for the target location.

5.1.1. Local Grid Format (Five Segments)

The local grid format is employed when the target coordinates fall within a mapped administrative zone at administrative level 8 or above (sub-prefecture, commune, village, neighbourhood, or quartier). The resulting code comprises five hyphen-delimited segments:

GN - CON - QYTC - B0B1 - 2282

Segment	Name	Description
GN	Country	ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 country code [8] (e.g., GN for Guinea)
CON	Region	3-character OGLAP code for the administrative level 4 or 6 region (e.g., CON for Conakry)
QYTC	Zone	1 to 8 (maximum) character code identifying the immediate administrative locality (level 8+), derived algorithmically from the locality name and its parent subdivision, or assigned explicitly via the localities naming file when manual curation is required
B0B1	Zone Macrobloc	4-character grid reference (Letter-Digit-Letter-Digit) encoding the 100m x 100m cell within the zone's bounding box
2282	Microspot	4-digit offset (XX = east metres, YY = north metres) within the macrobloc, yielding sub-metre precision

5.1.2. National Grid Format (Four Segments)

The national grid format is employed as a fallback when the target coordinates fall within a recognised region but outside any mapped administrative zone at level 8 or above. This ensures complete territorial coverage even in areas with sparse administrative boundary data:

GN - NZE - AABCDE - 4250

Segment	Name	Description
GN	Country	ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 country code [8]
NZE	Region	3-character OGLAP regional code
AABCDE	Regional Macrobloc	6-character national grid reference (A-Z per axis, $26^3 = 17,576$ per axis), encoding a 100m cell relative to the country's south-west anchor
4250	Microspot	4-digit offset within the national macrobloc cell

B0B1-2282 Yattaya Fossede, Conakry, Guinea

Figure 1: OGLAP Grid System Visualization

Reference address: B0B1-2282 Yattaya Fossede, Conakry, Guinea

Schematic representation of the OGLAP grid hierarchy showing country, region, zone, macrobloc (100m × 100m cells), and microspot (1m × 1m precision) layers.

The LAP code GN-CON-QYTC-B0B1-2282 encodes a location 22 metres east and 82 metres north within macrobloc B0B1 of the Yattaya Fossedè zone in Conakry region, in Guinea.

Note: This figure is a schematic illustration intended to convey the hierarchical structure of the protocol. Because its layers span widely different spatial scales, the representation are not drawn to scale; relative sizes and distances are adjusted for legibility and should not be read as exact measurements.

5.2. The Three Configuration Files

OGLAP's country-agnostic portability is achieved through the externalisation of all country-specific data into three JSON configuration files. These files constitute the centralised source of truth for any OGLAP deployment and must be prepared in conformity with the protocol's documented schemas.

File	Purpose	Contents
{cc}_oglap_country_profile.json	Country Profile	Grid parameters (cell sizes, encoding formats, letter mappings), administrative resolution rules (fallback hierarchies for region identification), zone naming conventions (type prefixes, stopword lists, consonant definitions, collision strategies), country extent and bounding box coordinates, package compatibility version ranges, and coordinate reference system specifications.
{cc}_localities_naming.json	Localities Naming	GeoJSON geometries for all administrative divisions (regions, prefectures, sub-prefectures, villages, quartiers), with pre-computed OGLAP zone codes, place identifiers, and hierarchical parent-child relationships. Generated from authoritative geospatial data (e.g., OpenStreetMap administrative boundaries [9], or national census data).
{cc}_full.json	Places Database	Complete geospatial reference dataset containing place records with GeoJSON geometries, structured address objects, OpenStreetMap metadata (place type, administrative level, display name), and bounding box information. Serves as the spatial lookup corpus for reverse geocoding and place resolution.

This three-file architecture ensures that the OGLAP encoding engine is entirely stateless with respect to country-specific knowledge. To deploy OGLAP in a new jurisdiction, the implementation remains unchanged; only the configuration files require preparation.

Each configuration file is identified by a versioned schema identifier that the reference engine validates at initialisation. Initialisation performs a structured pre-flight that verifies schema presence, required country and grid fields, country bounds geometry, package-version compatibility (declared as a caret-ranged “oglap_package_range” in the profile’s compatibility section), and dataset-version alignment between the profile and the localities naming file. The engine returns a deterministic report enumerating every check as pass, warn, or fail, and refuses to apply state if any fatal condition is detected, ensuring that mismatched, malformed, or stale configurations cannot silently degrade encoding accuracy.

The reference SDKs support two initialisation modes built on this validation contract. In direct mode, a host application supplies the profile and localities naming objects already loaded in memory, appropriate for browser-only or pre-bundled deployments. In download mode, the SDK retrieves a pinned dataset version from an OGLAP distribution origin, persists the three files to a local cache directory (organised by version), and reuses the cache on subsequent runs unless re-download is explicitly requested. Streamed downloads expose progress and slow-network signals to the host, and the validation pre-flight runs in both modes before any engine state is applied.

5.3. Zone Code Generation Algorithm

The zone code (the third segment of a local LAP code) is generated through a deterministic algorithm that derives a compact identifier (four characters in the base case, extending up to eight when collision resolution requires further disambiguation) from the locality's name and its position within the administrative hierarchy. Explicit zone codes pre-declared in the localities naming file take precedence over algorithmic generation and are reserved before the algorithm runs, allowing manual curation of high-priority or culturally significant locality codes without disturbing determinism elsewhere. When no explicit code is present, the algorithm proceeds as follows:

1. Name Normalisation: The locality name undergoes Unicode NFC normalisation, accent removal (NFD decomposition with diacritical mark stripping), uppercasing, conversion of hyphens and underscores to spaces, removal of specified punctuation characters, and whitespace collapse. This produces a canonical representation invariant to typographic variation.

2. Stopword Removal: A configurable set of French and locality-type stopwords (e.g., LE, LA, DE, QUARTIER, VILLAGE, PREFECTURE) is removed from the tokenised name, yielding significant tokens that carry discriminative semantic content.

3. Type Prefix Assignment: The first character of the zone code is determined by the OSM place type or administrative level of the locality (Q for quartier/neighbourhood, S for sub-prefecture/commune, V for village/hamlet, P for town/city, Z for generic locality, etc.), drawn from a configurable prefix map defined in the country profile .json file.

4. Consonant Extraction: Characters 2 and 3 are derived from the first two consonants (excluding A, E, I, O, U, Y) found in the concatenated significant tokens. If fewer than two consonants are available, the configurable padding character (default: X) is used.

5. Upper Administrative Letter: The fourth character is the first letter of the direct parent administrative subdivision (typically the prefecture or county), providing hierarchical disambiguation. Fallbacks proceed through the profile-defined priority chain: county name, state name, ISO code lookup, point-in-polygon containment, and ultimately the padding character.

5.4. Grid Encoding: Local and National Strategies

OGLAP employs two complementary grid encoding strategies to ensure complete territorial coverage:

Local Grid: The local grid is anchored to the south-west corner of the target zone's bounding box. The offset from this origin to the target coordinate is computed in metres using the WGS84 approximation (111,320 metres per degree of latitude; $111,320 \times \cos(\text{latitude})$ metres per degree of longitude). The east and north offsets are decomposed into 100-metre macrobloc cells and sub-metre microspot offsets. The macrobloc is encoded as a four-character sequence (Letter-Digit-Letter-Digit, where letters A through J represent tens digits 0 through 9), yielding a capacity of $100 \times 100 = 10,000$ cells per zone. The microspot is

encoded as four decimal digits (two for east, two for north), yielding one-metre precision within each cell.

National Grid: The national grid is anchored to the south-west corner of the country's bounding box. The macrobloc is encoded as a six-character sequence (three A-Z letters for east, three for north), where each three-letter group represents a base-26 integer (AAA = 0, ZZZ = 17,575), yielding a capacity of $17,576 \times 100$ metres = 1,757.6 kilometres per axis.

The 1,757.6 km per-axis capacity is sufficient for most nations. However, several countries with larger geographic extents exceed this span. For example, the Democratic Republic of Congo spans approximately 2,345 kilometres north-south, and Brazil, Russia, and Canada exceed 1,757.6 kilometres in various dimensions. For these territories, the protocol architecture supports extension to a four-letter encoding scheme ($26^4 = 456,976$ cells per axis, yielding 45,697 km per axis), though this extension is not yet implemented in the current reference deployment.

Distance Modes: The metres-per-degree conversion that drives both grid strategies is configurable per country via the profile's "grid_settings.distance_mode" field. The default "flat" mode applies a fixed constant (111,320 metres per degree of latitude; $111,320 \times \cos(\text{latitude})$ per degree of longitude), guaranteeing that previously published LAP codes remain byte-stable across profile revisions. New deployments may opt into "wgs84_ellipsoid" mode, which substitutes NOAA polynomial approximations of the WGS84 ellipsoid accurate to better than one millimetre per degree. Because switching modes changes every code produced under the affected profile, the validation pre-flight rejects unknown values rather than silently falling back, and the choice is treated as immutable for any country with codes already in circulation.

Antimeridian Handling: For countries whose longitude range spans the 180° meridian (for example Fiji, Kiribati, or the Russia / United States Aleutian span), the country bounds are detected as wrapped when the north-east longitude is numerically smaller than the south-west longitude. Under this condition, the grid arithmetic normalises any longitude west of the origin by adding 360° before measuring eastward offset, and decoded longitudes that overflow past +180° are wrapped back into the valid WGS84 range. Spatial indexing applies the same treatment: place bounding boxes that cross the antimeridian are split into two index entries pointing at the same place, so candidate lookups on either side of the meridian remain consistent.

5.5. Deterministic Collision Resolution

Stage 1 - Base Code: Attempt to assign the algorithmically generated base code (type prefix + two consonants + upper administrative letter). If the code is unoccupied within the region, assignment succeeds.

Stage 2 - Fallback A: If the base code is occupied, generate an alternative using the first letter of the state (rather than the county) as the fourth character. If this alternative is unoccupied, assignment succeeds.

Stage 3 - Alphanumeric Suffix Expansion: If both the base code and Fallback A are occupied, the engine appends a deterministic suffix drawn from a 36-character alphabet (digits 0-9 followed by letters A-Z), starting with single-character suffixes and continuing into multi-character base-36 indices as further disambiguation is required. Zone codes may grow up to eight characters in total, which yields effectively unbounded capacity ($36^5 \approx 60$ million distinct suffixes per three-character prefix) for any single region bucket. The engine raises a hard error if this capacity is ever exhausted, surfacing the underlying data anomaly rather than silently producing duplicate codes.

Critically, localities are processed in deterministic order (sorted by place identifier ascending), ensuring that the collision resolution produces identical assignments on every execution. Pre-computed zone code assignments from the localities naming file take precedence over algorithmic generation, permitting manual curation of high-priority or culturally significant locality codes.

5.6. Reverse Geocoding and Spatial Indexing

OGLAP's reverse geocoding engine identifies the administrative context of arbitrary coordinates through a spatial containment algorithm that tests point-in-polygon membership against all loaded GeoJSON geometries. The engine returns the smallest containing administrative boundary, then bubbles up missing hierarchical addressing properties (country, state, county, city) from enclosing parent boundaries. Bounding boxes and polygon areas are computed once and cached per place, optimising repeated lookups in memory-constrained environments. The country border polygon (administrative level 2) is separately cached for rapid boundary rejection of out-of-territory coordinates.

To keep containment queries efficient at production scale, the engine builds a static R-tree index (Flatbush) over place bounding boxes when the dataset is loaded. Candidate selection runs in $O(\log N + K)$ time, after which point-in-polygon membership is verified only against the small set of bounding-box matches. Bounding boxes that cross the antimeridian are deliberately split into two index entries pointing at the same place, so a query on either side of the 180° meridian still matches. Both bounding-box and polygon-area computations are memoised per place using WeakMaps, which guarantees that the engine never mutates the caller's input objects, a property required by the deterministic-encoding invariant, since later clicks must not be able to perturb the address resolution of earlier ones.

When multiple candidate polygons contain a query coordinate, the engine selects the place with the smallest area as the most specific match, breaking ties deterministically by ascending numeric place identifier (and lexicographic identifier as a final fallback). The address bubble-up that follows operates on a non-mutating copy of the selected place's address, layering in country, state, county, and sub-prefecture fields from successively larger enclosing polygons only when those fields are absent. This separation preserves the raw place address as the input to zone-code generation, which is what guarantees identical LAP codes across runs regardless of click order or query history.

Input Validation Gates: The encoder applies four layered safeguards before any spatial work begins, so that malformed or out-of-territory input cannot produce a misleading code.

Coordinates are first checked for finiteness (NaN, Infinity, and non-numeric values are rejected outright). They are then range-checked against the WGS84 envelope (latitude in [-90, 90], longitude in [-180, 180]). Surviving inputs face a fast-reject against the country's bounding box, computed in antimeridian-safe form. Finally, the country border polygon (administrative level 2) is consulted to confirm that the coordinate lies within national territory. Only coordinates that pass all four gates reach the R-tree candidate search, which keeps the engine's behaviour predictable under adversarial or sensor-noisy inputs.

6. Comprehensive Comparative Analysis

The following comparative analysis evaluates OGLAP against the two incumbent digital addressing systems across the dimensions most critical to deployment in developing nations.

Dimension	What3Words	Plus Codes (OLC)	OGLAP
Licensing Model	Proprietary, patented, closed-source; aggressive IP enforcement	Open source (Apache 2.0); no restrictions	MIT + Attribution; no restrictions.
Offline Capability	Recently added; historically required connectivity	Full offline support; no lookup tables needed	Full offline support; three config files loaded once at initialisation
Code Format	Three natural-language words (e.g., ///slurs.this.shark)	Alphanumeric (e.g., 7FG8+5VQ8)	Hierarchical segments (e.g., GN-CON-QYTC-B0B1-2282)
Spatial Precision	3m × 3m cells	~3.5m at max; ~14m standard	1m × 1m microspot within 100m cells
Spatial Intuition	Low; words are arbitrarily mapped and do not reflect geography or hierarchy	Low; codes are purely geometric and grid-based with no intuitive spatial meaning	High; hierarchical and territorially anchored structure enables users to infer approximate location, direction, and administrative belonging directly from the code
Administrative Context	None; codes are geographically abstract	None; codes are geographically abstract	Full: country, region, locality, and sub-locality encoded in code segments
Memorability	High for effective literate speakers; problematic for low-literacy individuals	Medium; extended alphanumeric requires learning and practice	Moderate-high; short segments with mnemonic administrative context; suitable for limited literacy
Address Disambiguation	Cases of confusion reported in field operations [4], [5], [6]; requires study	Medium; shortened codes require ~40km context	Low; hierarchical structure provides natural disambiguation at each level
Government Adoption Readiness	Proprietary dependency presents challenges for sovereign infrastructure	Medium; open source but abstract and non-territorial	High; designed for institutional adoption with territorial anchoring
Business Continuity Risk	Subject to ordinary commercial risks	Low; open source and Google-backed	None; MIT + Attribution, community-governed, no commercial dependency
Low-Literacy Suitability	Unvalidated in target contexts; word-based format requires literacy	Alphanumeric format, the short code may be accessible to basic literacy, while the full code may present challenges	Designed for alphabetic + numeric segments accessible to basic literacy
Scalability (New Countries)	Requires company action; per-language word lists	Universal; no configuration needed	Country-agnostic protocol; new deployment requires three JSON config files
Data Sovereignty	Data flows through commercial servers	Algorithm open; Not customizable and practical use tied to Google Maps	Fully sovereign; Dataset can be customized by State institutions, all data and logic execute locally

7. Strengths of the OGLAP Protocol

7.1. Administrative Territorial Anchoring

OGLAP's main differentiating approach is the systematic anchoring of location codes within the existing administrative territorial hierarchy of the target country. Beyond a label, it is a structural architectural decision that permeates every level of the encoding scheme.

When a Guinean citizen reads the code GN-CON-QYTC-B0B1-2282, the code itself communicates that the location is in Guinea (GN), in the Conakry region (CON), in the Yattaya Fossedè locality (QYTC), at a specific grid reference within that locality. This hierarchical transparency enables several capabilities that abstract geocoding systems cannot provide: postal sorting can be performed mechanically by parsing code prefixes; administrative statistics can be aggregated by code segment; emergency dispatchers can route responses based on regional and locality codes without consulting a lookup table; and citizens can verify the plausibility of an address by recognising familiar administrative names within the code structure.

This anchoring is achieved through the zone code generation algorithm's use of locality names, type prefixes derived from administrative levels, and upper administrative letters drawn from parent subdivisions. The result is a code that functions simultaneously as a spatial reference and an administrative classifier, a double utility that neither What3Words nor Plus Codes can offer.

7.2. Offline-First Architecture

OGLAP's offline-first design is a foundational architectural commitment. The protocol is engineered such that once the three configuration files have been loaded into an application's local environment, whether a mobile device, an embedded system, or a serverless function all encoding and decoding operations execute with zero network dependency. There is no API endpoint to query, no authentication token to refresh, no cloud service whose availability determines system functionality.

This architecture is critically important for the target deployment contexts. In rural Guinea, in informal settlements across Sub-Saharan Africa, in disaster-affected zones where telecommunications infrastructure has been compromised, OGLAP continues to function with full fidelity. The encoding algorithm requires only arithmetic operations on floating-point coordinates and string manipulation on cached configuration data. The computational cost is negligible on modern mobile processors, and the memory footprint of the configuration files is measured in single-digit megabytes.

7.3. Cognitive Accessibility and Low-Literacy Suitability

OGLAP's code format is specifically designed for populations whose formal education has primarily equipped them with alphabetic recognition and basic numeracy - precisely the skill profile that characterises the majority of adults in the target deployment regions.

The code structure leverages several cognitive accessibility principles. Each segment is short (two to four characters), reducing the working memory burden. The segments are

heterogeneous in character composition (letters, letter-digit mixtures, pure digits), providing visual distinctiveness that aids recognition and recall. The hierarchical structure enables contextual abbreviation: within a known locality, a citizen need only communicate the macrobloc and microspot segments (eight characters total) to specify a location, relying on shared contextual knowledge to supply the higher-level segments.

Critically, OGLAP avoids both the pronunciation ambiguity of word-based systems (where homophones, dialectal variation, and autocorrect errors introduce confusion) and the cognitive load of extended alphanumeric sequences (where the absence of semantic scaffolding makes recall and transcription error-prone). The result is a format that occupies a productive middle ground: more structured and territorially informative than words, more memorable and parsimonious than raw coordinates or long character strings.

7.4. Open Source Governance and Transparency

OGLAP's release under the MIT License with Attribution represents a deliberate governance decision tuned for adoption in sovereign and institutional contexts. The MIT License is one of the most permissive widely used open-source licences: it permits unrestricted use, modification, distribution, and integration into proprietary as well as open-source systems, subject only to the requirement that the original copyright notice and attribution be preserved. The attribution clause ensures that the protocol's origin remains transparent to downstream users, while the licence's permissive posture removes legal friction for governments, postal authorities, humanitarian agencies, and private-sector implementers who may need to embed OGLAP within existing software stacks subject to heterogeneous licensing regimes.

For governments evaluating digital addressing systems, this licensing posture eliminates several categories of risk that attend proprietary alternatives: the risk of vendor lock-in, the risk of licensing fee escalation, the risk of service discontinuation, and the risk of algorithmic opacity in critical infrastructure. OGLAP can be audited line by line, modified to suit local requirements, and governed by the community of its users rather than by a distant commercial entity.

7.5. Country-Agnostic Portability

The OGLAP protocol's three-file configuration architecture ensures that the encoding engine is entirely agnostic to the specific country in which it operates. The protocol specification defines schemas for the country profile, localities naming, and places database files; any country that prepares these three files in conformity with the schemas can immediately deploy OGLAP without modifying the encoding engine.

This portability is of particular significance for regional and continental addressing initiatives. A consortium of West African nations, for example, could adopt OGLAP as a shared addressing standard, with each member state maintaining its own configuration files while sharing a common protocol specification and software implementation. The ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 country code prefix ensures global uniqueness across deployments.

7.6. Deterministic Reproducibility

OGLAP's encoding algorithm is purely deterministic: identical input coordinates, processed against identical configuration data, will always produce identical LAP codes, regardless of the device, operating system, basemap, display language, or time of execution. This determinism is guaranteed by the protocol's explicit stability contract, which specifies that LAP codes are basemap-independent, label-language-independent, and depend only on reference data and mathematical formulas.

This property is essential for applications where addressing must be legally reliable: land registration, property taxation, contract specification, judicial proceedings, and census enumeration. A LAP code recorded today will resolve to the same coordinates and administrative context when queried years hence, provided the configuration data has not been versioned forward (in which case the version history provides a complete audit trail).

7.7. Dual-Grid Resilience

OGLAP's dual-grid architecture (local grids anchored to administrative zone bounding boxes, with a national grid fallback for unmapped areas) ensures that the system provides complete territorial coverage even when administrative boundary data is incomplete. In areas where OpenStreetMap or national cadastral data provides detailed boundary polygons, the local grid delivers administratively anchored codes with maximum contextual information. In areas where only regional boundaries are available, the national grid ensures that every coordinate within the country's territory receives a valid, decodable LAP code.

This resilience is architecturally distinctive. Neither What3Words nor Plus Codes face the same design challenge, as neither attempts to integrate with administrative boundaries. But for a system that stakes its utility on territorial anchoring, the graceful degradation from local to national grid, without breaking the code format or requiring special handling by consuming applications, is a critical engineering achievement. The switch is governed by two conditions that the encoder evaluates per coordinate: the containing administrative place must be at admin_level 9 or higher (sub-prefecture, village, or quartier), and the locality must either expose a meaningful name (yielding at least one significant token after stopword removal) or carry an explicit zone code from the localities naming file. When either condition fails, the encoder transparently falls back to the national grid rather than producing a degenerate zone segment.

7.8. Human-Readable Address Generation

Beyond the LAP code itself, OGLAP's encoding engine produces a human-readable address string (the humanAddress field) that translates the code's hierarchical segments into natural-language place names. For example, the LAP code GN-CON-QYTC-B0B1-2282 resolves to the human-readable address “B0B1-2282 Yattaya Fossedè, Conakry, Guinée.” This dual output, comprising a machine-readable code and a human-readable address, supports both automated processing and human communication, a design consideration that neither incumbent system provides natively.

7.9. Spatial Orientation and Navigability

A distinctive feature of OGLAP is that its macrobloc and microspot segments encode directional offset information, unlike abstract geocoding systems such as What3Words and Plus Codes. The macrobloc segment identifies a specific 100-metre by 100-metre cell, and the microspot segment encodes the east and north offsets in metres from the cell's south-west corner. This structure provides intuitive spatial orientation and navigability:

Users can mentally orient themselves within the grid by understanding that the first pair of digits in the microspot represents metres travelled east, and the second pair represents metres travelled north. Two people sharing OGLAP codes can estimate relative distance and direction without consulting a basemap or external reference. Navigation becomes intuitive: to travel east, increase the first pair of microspot digits; to travel north, increase the second pair. This is especially powerful for delivery and emergency services in areas without structured street names, where the ability to communicate direction and relative position can significantly improve navigation efficiency and response time.

This spatial orientation capability represents a fundamental difference in how the addressing system supports human spatial cognition and communication.

8. Limitations, Risks, and Mitigation Strategies

Intellectual honesty demands acknowledgment of OGLAP's current limitations alongside its strengths. The following assessment identifies the principal risks and constraints, together with the mitigation strategies that the protocol's architecture affords.

Dependency on Administrative Boundary Data Quality: OGLAP's local grid accuracy is contingent on the quality and completeness of the GeoJSON administrative boundary data in the localities naming file. In regions where OpenStreetMap coverage is sparse [9], [11] or where administrative boundaries are disputed, the system may fall back to the national grid more frequently than desired. Mitigation: The protocol's dual-grid architecture provides graceful degradation. Additionally, the configuration files can be progressively enriched as boundary data improves, with backward-compatible versioning ensuring that previously issued codes remain valid.

National Grid Span Limitation: The three-letter encoding of the national grid macrobloc (26^3 cells) yields a per-axis capacity of 1,757.6 kilometres. While this is sufficient for most countries, nations with larger geographic extents, such as the Democratic Republic of Congo (north-south extent $\sim 2,345$ km), Brazil ($\sim 2,766$ km east-west), Russia ($\sim 9,000$ km), and Canada ($\sim 5,500$ km east-west), exceed this span in one or more dimensions. Mitigation: The protocol architecture supports extension to four-letter encoding (26^4 cells per axis = 45,697 km capacity), which would accommodate all nations. This extension is not yet implemented but is feasible through configuration file and encoding engine updates.

Initial Configuration Burden: Deploying OGLAP in a new country requires the preparation of three JSON configuration files, a process that demands geospatial expertise, access to authoritative boundary data, and familiarity with the protocol's schema specifications. This is a higher initial investment than Plus Codes (which require no configuration) or W3W (which is pre-configured globally by the vendor), but is instrumental to allow full State sovereignty on the country addressing system. Mitigation: The reference implementation includes tooling for automated generation of configuration files from OpenStreetMap data, reducing the manual effort to curation and validation rather than creation ex nihilo.

Limited Current Deployment: As of the date of this publication, OGLAP is being deployed in production only in the Republic of Guinea, by “Kiraa” navigation app, available in Play Store and App Store. While the protocol is designed for country-agnostic portability, the absence of multi-country deployment data limits empirical validation of its claims. Mitigation: The Guinea deployment serves as a comprehensive reference implementation and proof of concept. The open-source nature of the protocol enables independent replication and validation by interested parties.

Code Length: A full local-grid LAP code (e.g., GN-CON-QYTC-B0B1-2282) comprises 20 characters including delimiters. For oral communication and manual transcription, this length may present challenges. Mitigation: The hierarchical structure enables contextual abbreviation. Within a known region and locality, only the macrobloc and microspot segments (B0B1-2282, nine characters) need to be communicated, substantially reducing the effective length.

Absence of Formal Usability Validation: While OGLAP's design incorporates cognitive accessibility principles, the protocol has not yet been subjected to formal usability testing with representative low-literacy populations. Mitigation: Formal usability research is a priority for the project's next phase, with pilot studies planned in partnership with Guinean educational and civic institutions.

9. Use Cases and Deployment Scenarios

Postal Service Modernisation: National postal authorities can adopt OGLAP codes as the foundation of a digital postal addressing system, enabling mechanised sorting by parsing code prefixes (country → region → locality) and last-mile delivery using macrobloc and microspot segments. The hierarchical structure directly maps to the operational organisation of postal distribution networks.

Emergency Response Dispatch: Emergency service dispatchers can use LAP codes to identify the administrative jurisdiction and approximate location of a caller without consulting external databases. The regional and locality codes enable immediate routing to the correct response unit, while the macrobloc and microspot segments guide field teams to the precise location.

Land Registration and Cadastral Systems: Governments can use LAP codes as supplementary identifiers in land registration systems, providing a standardised, machine-readable location reference that complements parcel numbers and plot descriptions. The deterministic nature of the encoding ensures long-term stability for legal instruments that reference specific locations.

Census and Statistical Enumeration: National statistics offices can use OGLAP codes to georeference census data at sub-metre resolution, enabling fine-grained spatial analysis while maintaining alignment with the administrative boundaries used for statistical reporting. Aggregation by code segment supports multi-scale analysis from national to neighbourhood level.

E-Commerce and Logistics: Logistics providers operating in address-deficient regions can use LAP codes as delivery addresses, enabling automated route planning based on the hierarchical code structure. The offline capability ensures that delivery drivers can resolve addresses in areas without mobile data coverage.

Humanitarian Operations: International humanitarian organisations operating in conflict or disaster zones can use OGLAP codes to coordinate resource distribution, population tracking, and infrastructure mapping. The offline-first design is particularly valuable in contexts where telecommunications infrastructure has been compromised. Where the underlying place data exposes UN OCHA pcodes, the encoder surfaces them alongside the generated LAP, so OGLAP outputs can be joined directly against pcode-keyed humanitarian datasets (3W matrices, IDP tracking systems, Common Operational Datasets) without an intermediate lookup.

Financial Inclusion: Banks and microfinance institutions can accept LAP codes as domicile verification, enabling address-dependent financial services for populations that currently lack the formal street addresses required by regulatory compliance frameworks.

10. Licensing, Governance, and Intellectual Property

OGLAP is released under the MIT License with Attribution [10], one of the most permissive and widely deployed open-source licences. This choice reflects a deliberate strategy to maximise institutional, governmental, and commercial uptake without imposing copyleft obligations on integrators, while still preserving authorship transparency through a mandatory attribution clause. The licence was selected with the following governance objectives in mind:

Perpetual Freedom: The MIT License guarantees that the reference implementation will remain freely available in perpetuity. The published source code may be used, copied, modified, merged, distributed, sublicensed, and sold without licensing fees, without seeking permission, and without restriction on the field of endeavour.

Attribution Preservation: The licence requires that the original copyright notice and attribution to Guinee IO be preserved in all copies and substantial portions of the software. This keeps OGLAP's authorship transparent to downstream users, supports academic and institutional citation, and protects the protocol's identity across forks and embedded deployments without imposing further obligations on integrators.

Commercial and Institutional Compatibility: The MIT License integrates cleanly with proprietary, open-source, and hybrid software stacks, and is compatible with virtually every other open-source licence in widespread institutional use. This removes legal review friction for postal authorities, telecommunications regulators, banks, logistics providers, and humanitarian agencies that operate under heterogeneous procurement and compliance regimes, and ensures that OGLAP can be embedded into closed-source mobile applications, vendor SDKs, and government information systems without triggering copyleft obligations.

Patent Posture: While the MIT License does not by itself include an express patent grant, Guinee IO holds no patents over the OGLAP protocol, the LAP code format, or the reference implementation, and has no intention to file any. The protocol is published as prior art, and the project will not pursue defensive or offensive patent claims against good-faith implementers. This posture is reaffirmed in the project's public governance statements and is intended to give regulators and institutional adopters the same practical patent assurance that a copyleft licence would provide, without the redistribution constraints.

The copyright is held by Guinee IO, with the source code publicly hosted on GitHub at github.com/Guinee-IO/oglap-ggp-node-js. Contributions are accepted under a Contributor Licence Agreement that assigns copyright to the project while granting perpetual, irrevocable rights to the contributor.

11. Conclusion and Recommendations

The global addressing crisis demands solutions that are architecturally aligned with the institutional, cognitive, and infrastructural realities of the communities they serve. The two incumbent digital addressing systems, What3Words and Google Plus Codes, represent meaningful but ultimately insufficient responses to this crisis. What3Words delivers literacy ready memorability at the cost of proprietary enclosure, algorithmic opacity, and documented cases of directional failure in field operations [4], [5], [6]. Plus Codes deliver technical transparency and openness at the cost of cognitive accessibility and administrative relevance.

OGLAP charts a different course. By anchoring location codes within the administrative territorial structure of the target country, OGLAP produces addresses that are simultaneously machine-readable spatial references and human-intelligible administrative classifiers. By committing to offline-first determinism, OGLAP ensures reliability in the connectivity-constrained environments where digital addressing is most urgently needed. By adopting the MIT License with Attribution, OGLAP guarantees that the protocol will remain freely available, auditable, and embeddable across the full range of public and private software stacks in which addressing infrastructure must operate.

The protocol is not without limitations. Its dependency on administrative boundary data quality, the span limitations of the three-letter national grid encoding for the largest nations, its initial configuration burden, and its limited deployment history are acknowledged constraints that must be addressed through continued development, community engagement, and empirical validation. But these limitations are remediable: they are engineering and adoption challenges, not architectural deficiencies.

We respectfully recommend that government authorities, postal services, international development organisations, and technology implementers evaluate OGLAP as a sovereign, open-source alternative to proprietary and abstract addressing systems. The protocol's reference implementation for Guinea is production-ready, openly available, and documented to a standard that supports independent replication and assessment.

The right to a verifiable address is, in its practical consequences, a precondition for the exercise of many other rights. OGLAP represents a commitment to ensuring that this precondition is met through open, transparent, and institutionally embedded technology.

12. Next Steps and Development Roadmap

12.1. Refinement of the Guinea Country Profile (Priority: Immediate)

Collaboration with the Ministère du Plan et de la Coopération Internationale and the Ministère de l'Administration du Territoire et de la Décentralisation to refine the country profile and administrative geometry data. Specifically, alignment of OGLAP's administrative boundary data with the official territorial divisions as defined by the Recensement Général de la Population et de l'Habitation (RGPH-5), Guinea's most recent national census. This will ensure more accurate administrative delineation at all levels (regions, prefectures, sub-prefectures, communes, and quartiers), and strengthen the protocol's institutional legitimacy.

12.2. Multi-Country Expansion (Priority: Medium-Term)

Extension of OGLAP deployment to additional countries, beginning with West African nations sharing similar administrative structures and addressing challenges. This requires preparation of country profile, localities naming, and places database files for each target jurisdiction. The protocol's country-agnostic architecture makes this a data preparation exercise rather than an engineering one. Priority targets include Senegal, Mali, Sierra Leone, and Côte d'Ivoire.

12.3. Data Optimisation and File Size Reduction (Priority: Ongoing)

Optimisation of the three configuration files to reduce storage footprint and initialisation time, particularly for resource-constrained mobile devices. Strategies under investigation include geometry simplification (reducing polygon vertex count while preserving boundary accuracy), binary serialisation formats, differential updates, and on-demand lazy loading of regional data subsets.

12.4. Four-Letter National Grid Extension (Priority: Pending Need)

Specification and implementation of the four-letter national macrobloc encoding scheme ($26^4 = 456,976$ cells per axis, yielding 45,697 km per axis). The protocol architecture already accommodates this extension; implementation is gated on the first deployment in a country whose extent exceeds the 1,757.6 km per-axis capacity of the current three-letter scheme (notably the Democratic Republic of Congo, Brazil, Russia, and Canada). The extension is profile-driven and is designed to be backward-compatible: a profile that does not declare four-letter encoding continues to produce three-letter codes unchanged.

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Appendix A: OGLAP Code Format Specification

A.1 Local Grid LAP Code

Format: CC-RRR-ZZZZ-LDLD-NNNN

Field	Length	Charset	Description
CC	2	A-Z	ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 country code [8]
RRR	3	A-Z	OGLAP regional code (admin level 4/6)
ZZZZ...	1-8	A-Z, 0-9	Zone code. Base form is type prefix + consonant key + admin letter; it may extend up to 8 characters via a deterministic base-36 collision suffix, or be assigned explicitly via the localities naming file.
LDLD	4	A-J, 0-9	Local macrobloc (Letter-Digit-Letter-Digit)
NNNN	4	0-9	Microspot (east XX, north YY in metres)

A.2 National Grid LAP Code

Format: CC-RRR-AAAAA-NNNN

Field	Length	Charset	Description
CC	2	A-Z	ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 country code [8]
RRR	3	A-Z	OGLAP regional code
AAAAA	6	A-Z	National macrobloc (3 letters east + 3 letters north, base-26)
NNNN	4	0-9	Microspot (east XX, north YY in metres)

Accepted Input Forms (SDK convenience): The reference SDKs accept LAP codes in several equivalent shapes against an initialised country profile. The country prefix is optional, since the active profile already pins it: for example, “GN-CON-QYTC-B0B1-2282” and “CON-QYTC-B0B1-2282” resolve to the same coordinates. The SDKs also accept zone-search shorthands such as “CON QYTC” or “QYTC” for locality-level lookups. Hyphen and whitespace separators are interchangeable, and casing is normalised. These conveniences are SDK-level affordances; the canonical persistence form for storage, indexing, and inter-system exchange remains the fully prefixed code.

A.3 Grid Parameters

Parameter	Value	Notes
Macrobloc cell size	100 metres × 100 metres	Both local and national grids
Microspot resolution	1 metre × 1 metre	Sub-metre precision within each cell
Local grid capacity	100 × 100 cells per zone	10,000 cells = 10 km × 10 km (100 km ²) coverage per zone
National grid capacity	17,576 × 17,576 cells	1,757.6 km per axis (sufficient for most nations; larger nations require 4-letter extension)
Coordinate reference	WGS84 (EPSG:4326)	Standard GPS datum
Metres/degree latitude	111,320	Fixed WGS84 approximation
Metres/degree longitude	111,320 × cos(lat)	Latitude-dependent approximation

Appendix B: Glossary of Terms

Term	Definition
MIT License	A permissive free-software licence (Open Source Initiative approved) that allows unrestricted use, modification, distribution, and integration into proprietary or open-source software, subject only to preservation of the original copyright notice and attribution.
Administrative Level	A tier within a country's territorial governance hierarchy. Level 2 = country, Level 4 = region/state, Level 6 = prefecture/county, Level 8 = sub-prefecture/commune, Level 9-10 = village/quartier.
Bounding Box (bbox)	The minimum axis-aligned rectangle that encloses a geographic feature, defined by its south-west and north-east corners.
Copyleft	A licensing strategy that requires derivative works to be distributed under the same or compatible licence terms, preventing proprietary enclosure.
Deterministic	Producing identical outputs from identical inputs on every execution, regardless of environment.
GeoJSON	An open standard format for encoding geographic data structures using JavaScript Object Notation (JSON).
GGP	Global Grid Protocol. The specification framework upon which OGLAP's grid encoding and naming conventions are based.
LAP Code	Location Addressing Protocol code. The hierarchically structured alphanumeric identifier produced by the OGLAP encoding algorithm.
Macrobloc	A 100m × 100m grid cell within an OGLAP zone (local grid) or country (national grid).
Microspot	A 1m × 1m location within a macrobloc, encoded as a four-digit offset (east, north).
OGLAP	Offline Grid Location Addressing Protocol. The subject protocol of this white paper.
OSM	OpenStreetMap. A collaborative, open-source mapping project providing free geographic data.
Reverse Geocoding	The process of converting geographic coordinates into a human-readable address or administrative identifier.
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984. The standard coordinate reference system used by GPS and most mapping applications.
Antimeridian	The 180° meridian opposite the Greenwich prime meridian. OGLAP treats a country as antimeridian-crossing when its eastern bound longitude is numerically smaller than its western bound, and applies longitude normalisation in grid arithmetic and spatial indexing accordingly.
Distance Mode	The metres-per-degree conversion strategy declared in a country profile. "flat" uses a fixed constant (default 111,320 m/° latitude, scaled by cos(latitude) for longitude). "wgs84_ellipsoid" substitutes NOAA polynomial approximations of the WGS84 ellipsoid (sub-millimetre per degree). The choice is immutable for any country whose codes are already in circulation.
Pcode	Place code published by the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UN OCHA). Where a place carries a pcode in its OSM metadata, the OGLAP encoder surfaces it alongside the generated LAP code to ease integration with humanitarian datasets.
R-tree (Flatbush)	A static spatial index over bounding boxes that resolves point-containment candidates in O(log N + K) time. The OGLAP reference implementation uses Flatbush, a compact R-tree library suitable for browser and serverless environments.
Schema ID	A versioned identifier embedded in each OGLAP configuration file (currently "oglap.country_profile.v2" and "oglap.localities_naming.v1"). The reference engine validates the schema_id at initialisation and refuses to apply state if the file does not match a supported schema version.
Zone Code	A 1- to 8-character identifier within an OGLAP LAP code that represents the immediate administrative locality of a location. The base form is four characters; collision resolution may extend it up to eight, and explicit codes may be supplied via the localities naming file.

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